

ISic1276

I.Sicily inscription 1276

Language

Ancient Greek

Type

dedication

Material

marble

Object**Editor**

Jonathan Prag

Principal Contributor

Jonathan Prag

Contributors

Jonathan Prag,James Cummings,James Chartrand,Valeria Vitale,Michael Metcalfe,Alex Antoniou,Simona Stoyanova

Autopsy

No Autopsy

Last Change

2020-11-26 - Simona Stoyanova restructured bibliography

Place of origin (ancient)

Catina

Place of origin (modern)

Catania

Provenance**Coordinates****Current Location**

Italy, Sicily, Catania, Museo Civico di Catania, inventory 318

Physical Description

Dimensions

Height cm

Width cm

Depth cm

Layout

Execution

Engraved

Letter Forms

Letter heights:

Line 1: mm

Interlineation

Interlineation line 1 to 2: mm

Text

1. [Φ]οῖβον ἀκερσεκόμην
2. [ἐκ]ατηβόλον Ἀπόλλωνα
3. [ἰ]δρυσάμην σηκ[ῶτ'ἐπὶ]
4. κόσμον κ[αλὸνἔθηκα]
5. Πατρ

Apparatus

Korhonen 2004

Translation (en)

I raised a fine [statue of] long-haired Phoebus, far-shooting Apollo, in a sacred enclosure, and added decoration

Commentary

Digital identifiers:

TM 492882

EDCS 39101645

PHI 140765

PHI 316198

Bibliography

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Cite as:

J. Prag et al. (2020-12-18): ISic1276. <http://sicily.classics.ox.ac.uk>. (Collection: TEI edition). <http://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.4353341>